

Dynamic modeling of the activities of functional subsystems and enterprises in the housing and communal services sector

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Аннотация. Отсутствие понятной системы управления и наличие противоречий в достижении своих интересов между отраслевыми предприятиями сферы жилищно-коммунального хозяйства (ЖКХ) существенно снижает результаты их производственно-хозяйственной деятельности. Актуальность темы статьи определяется необходимостью реформирования социально значимой для российской экономики сферы ЖКХ, развитие рыночных методов управления, проведения комплексной модернизации всей инфраструктуры этой сферы, а также стимулирования отраслевых предприятий к повышению результатов и качества своей деятельности. Основной целью данной работы является поиск путей повышения эффективности функционирования отраслевых предприятий сферы ЖКХ в условиях комплексной модернизации. В качестве методологической основы исследования были использованы методы структурирования деятельности отраслевых предприятий сферы ЖКХ, а также динамического моделирования их неравновесных состояний с учетом функционально однородных по основной производственно-хозяйственной деятельности подсистем и влияния пространственных и временных факторов. Полученную в ходе проведения исследования динамическую модель неравновесных состояний функциональных экономических подсистем, можно использовать на практике применительно к уровню отдельных функциональных подсистем сферы ЖКХ и входящих в их состав предприятий в целях повышения эффективности их деятельности.

Abstract. The absence of a clear management system and the presence of contradictions in achieving their interests between industry enterprises in the sphere of housing and communal services (HCS) significantly reduces the results of their production and economic activities. The relevance of the topic of the article is determined by the need to reform the socially significant for the Russian economy housing and communal services sector, develop market management methods, carry out a comprehensive modernization of the entire infrastructure of this sector, as well as stimulate industry enterprises to improve the results and quality of their activities. The main goal of this work is to find ways to improve the efficiency of industry enterprises in the housing and communal services sector in the context of comprehensive modernization. As a methodological basis for the study, we used the methods of structuring the activities of industry enterprises in the housing and communal services sector, as well as dynamic modeling of their nonequilibrium states, taking into account functionally homogeneous subsystems in the main production and economic activities and the influence of spatial and temporal factors. The dynamic model of nonequilibrium states of functional economic subsystems obtained in the course of the study can be used in practice with respect to the level of individual functional subsystems of the housing and communal services sector and the enterprises included in their composition in order to improve the efficiency of their activities.

Ключевые слова: сфера ЖКХ, предприятия, структурирование, функциональные подсистемы, динамическое моделирование.

Keywords: housing and communal services sector, enterprises, structuring, functional subsystems, dynamic modeling.

Introduction

The housing and communal services sector is one of the problematic areas in the Russian economy. On the one hand, it ensures the vital activity of the population of the country, district, region, territory, city and objectively reflects the standard and quality of life. On the other hand, the activities of functional subsystems and enterprises in this sector raise many complaints, and the complex of unresolved problems continues to grow, despite the efforts of both the enterprises themselves and the governing bodies at the municipal, local, territorial, and regional levels. In the context of comprehensive modernization, the housing and communal services sector can be considered as a heterogeneous complex and multifunctional macrosystem of life support and safety of the

population, which includes various functional sectors and economic subsystems [1].

It is customary to distinguish three key sectors of this sphere, namely: housing stock; resource supply (heat, electricity, water, gas, sewerage); improvement of settlements and adjacent territories (road and bridge facilities, improvement, sanitary cleaning, waste disposal). From the standpoint of a systems approach, the housing and communal services sector is represented by: residential and public buildings; operating, repair and construction, transport, energy and other organizations and enterprises. Together, they constitute a complex socio-economic system, the functioning of which is ensured by industry enterprises. The level of development and quality of operation of urban and rural development, as well as the

improvement of the living environment of the population, depend on the effective operation of this system.

The strategic development of the housing and communal services sector is based on the implementation of the most effective measures and tools, as well as on resource provision, which are envisaged in the Strategy for the Development of the Construction Industry and Housing and Communal Services of the Russian Federation for the Period up to 2030 with a forecast up to 2035 [2]. The main goal of the functioning of the housing and communal services sector is the provision of all types of housing and communal services and, thereby, the satisfaction of the basic needs of urban and rural residents. The structure of the housing and communal services sector is represented by industry enterprises that sell homogeneous products or provide homogeneous services. At the same time, the industry enterprises themselves differ in the production technologies they use or the types of economic activity.

The key functional features of the activities of subsystems and their constituent industry enterprises in the housing and utilities sector in Russia are:

- a combination of production and non-production functions related to the production of material products and the provision of services;
- special social significance, which increases the need for state regulation and supervision of the quality of services and products provided;
- a combination of commercial (profit-oriented) and non-commercial activities;
- a combination of large (electricity production, water supply, utilities, pipeline networks, etc.) and small enterprises (management companies, utility service enterprises, etc.);
- special importance of environmental and sanitary-epidemiological control;
- the need to ensure the provision of minimum services regardless of the level of solvency of the population.

At present, the efficiency of the housing and utilities sector is subject to increased demands, both from the objective requirements of incremental improvement of the quality of the living environment of the population, and in connection with a significant lag in technical and organizational terms from the level of leading countries. The low dynamics of innovative development in this sector is due to a mass of accumulated problems that have been solved unsatisfactorily and inconsistently throughout the entire period of reforming the housing and utilities sector. Additional complexity was added by ill-considered transformations, an imbalance in the mechanism for the joint application of tariff and price regulation of services of resource supplying and management organizations, and a number of other factors [3].

Based on the above, it can be concluded that there are problems in the activities of functional subsystems and enterprises in the housing and communal services sector, the solution of which will contribute to progressive development. The authors believe that one of the approaches to solving them can be dynamic modeling of the activities of functional subsystems and enterprises in the housing and communal services sector. Since the previously used management models in the housing and communal services sector did not ensure the stable functioning of its subsystems and industry enterprises, as well as the required quality of housing and communal

services, this study seems relevant and has a practical focus.

Materials and methods

Based on the above reasoning, the housing and utilities sector can be represented as a certain set of interconnected industry subsystems, each of which specializes in the implementation of a certain function [4]. At the same time, each functional subsystem is represented by a fairly large set of enterprises and organizations with multidirectional interests in their activities. This is especially evident at the municipal level of governance [5]. Taking this circumstance into account, the state of each functional economic subsystem can be characterized by a set of

indicators $x_1^i(t), \dots, x_m^i(t)$, which represent the coordinates of the state vector $x^i(t)$ for the i -th subsystem. For functional economic subsystems, such indicators can be the volumes of serviced housing stock, supplies of utilities, provided housing and communal services (HCS), etc. [6].

The dynamics of interaction of enterprises within the functional subsystems in the process of comprehensive modernization of the housing and utilities sector can be described by a number of basic arguments, which are time and spatial factors [7]. By spatial factors we mean a certain set of parameters of the housing and utilities sector as a system that characterize one or another of its functional subsystems or industry enterprises. For this purpose, various indicators can be used, the presence of which generally indicates the heterogeneity of this sector, since most of these indicators are expressed in different units of measurement. Time factors allow, on the one hand, to take into account the dynamics of changes in the states of functional subsystems and industry enterprises in a certain time interval, and, on the other hand, the real speed of transformation of their states over time.

Almost all known approaches to modeling non-equilibrium states of functional subsystems are based on a formalized description and structuring of the housing and communal services sector by types of economic activity and the composition of enterprises performing certain functional-spatial components of this activity [8]. The activity of an individual enterprise is significantly subject to the influence of random factors, while the activity of some of their associations in the form of functional subsystems is subject to random factors to a lesser extent.

Functional subsystems in the housing and utilities sector can be considered, on the one hand, as a holistic entity, and, on the other hand, as a set of industry enterprises. With regard to a specific industry enterprise, the construction of dynamic models of nonequilibrium states of its activity and the identification of their interrelations with models of nonequilibrium states of activity of other enterprises is significantly complicated. To overcome these difficulties, simplified models are used that describe the formal behavior of a set of functional enterprises in highly aggregated conditions. In this case, the model of the studied set of enterprises is formed on the basis of functional structuring and simple forms of their interaction with each other. Naturally, this path is less complex and costly, and therefore more preferable.

Results and discussion

The principle of functional homogeneity of the main production and economic activity is the basis for structuring sectoral enterprises in the housing and utilities sector and their unification into economic subsystems. At the same time, the level of detail and the relationship of a specific enterprise to a particular functional subsystem will be determined by the set of functions that are essential in modeling the development strategies of most enterprises in this subsystem.

The result of such an approach to the decomposition of the housing and communal services sector is the allocation of homogeneous functional subsystems D^i ($i = 1, \dots, q$) in its composition. At the same time, in the process of its functioning, each of these subsystems experiences multidirectional effects of management factors - $V^u(t, x)$, factors of influence of the external environment - $V^v(t, x)$, factors of functioning of other subsystems - $V^s(t, x)$, which change in time and space. Taking into account the influence of the specified set of factors ensures the formation of the output result in the production activity of industry enterprises of a particular functional subsystem - $E^i(t, x)$.

Decomposition and structuring of the housing and utilities sector into functionally homogeneous subsystems can be considered as an innovative component of the implementation of a comprehensive modernization of this sector [10, 11]. This approach helps to form the structure of its model for further research in terms of modeling the development strategies of enterprises included in these subsystems. The formal structure of the housing and utilities sector can be represented by a graph that combines the above-mentioned subsystems and a set of multidirectional influencing factors, the detailing of which can be expressed conditionally through specific weights determined in the first approximation by the expert method. An important element of this kind of functional structures is the presence of interrelations between all or only individual components. It should be noted that in addition to graphs, other structures can be used when modeling subsystems of the housing and utilities sector. However, almost all possible structures can be divided into two large groups - with rigid and probabilistic connections between their elements.

The structure of the elements of the functional subsystem of the housing and communal services sector (G) will be considered rigid in the case when the interrelations between them take place and do not undergo significant changes during the period of its functioning under consideration. If such a structure is represented by a graph, then a fixed matrix J with elements $(0, 1)$ can be used to describe it, which has the following form:

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} 0001 \\ 0011 \\ 0101 \\ 1110 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Accordingly, the structure of the elements of the functional subsystem of the housing and

communal services sector will be considered probabilistic in the case when the interrelations between them take place, but they are predominantly random. From this follows the conclusion that there is not one structure, but a certain set of structures, the elements of which are a certain set of rigid structures G_1, \dots, G_m , which are realized with their own probabilities, characteristic only of them.

Among the methods of structuring the housing and utilities sector into functional subsystems, hierarchical methods have recently become the most widespread. Their distinctive feature is the presence of one or more levels of subordination, each of which can contain virtually any number of subsystems. At the same time, the relationship between functional subsystems is unidirectional, in which upper-level subsystems influence lower-level subsystems. Formally, using a hierarchical structure, it is quite easy to describe the functional sequence of relationships between subsystems of the housing and utilities sector D^i ($i = 1, \dots, q$):

$$D^{i_1} \succ D^{i_2} \succ \dots \succ D^{i_q} \quad (2)$$

where i_1, \dots, i_q – numbers from the set $1, \dots, q$;

\succ – hierarchical relationship presence operator.

The above sequence assumes that there is only one subsystem at each level, which means that it can be used to describe the relationships between rigid hierarchical structures. For probabilistic hierarchical structures, each subsystem can have its own level of subordination with some probability. In this case, the above sequence acquires a random character [12]. However, the number of such sequences will always be finite due to the finiteness of the number of subordination levels and the subsystems under consideration. For example, for three levels of subordination and three subsystems, provided that there can only be one subsystem at each level, the number of possible probabilistic hierarchical structures is limited to six options: $D_1 \rightarrow D_2 \rightarrow D_3$ (1); $D_1 \rightarrow D_3 \rightarrow D_2$ (2); $D_2 \rightarrow D_1 \rightarrow D_3$ (3); $D_2 \rightarrow D_3 \rightarrow D_1$ (4); $D_3 \rightarrow D_1 \rightarrow D_2$ (5); $D_3 \rightarrow D_2 \rightarrow D_1$ (6).

Thus, for a probabilistic hierarchical structure, the sequence of relationships between its elements will be fulfilled with some probability

$$P = \{ D^{i_1} \succ D^{i_2} \succ \dots \succ D^{i_q} \} = p_m, \quad (3)$$

where m – permutation number of q indices (i_1, \dots, i_q) , $m = 1, \dots, q$.

This expression defines a discrete probability distribution function (p_m) on a set of hierarchical structures.

It seems obvious that the enterprises included in the functionally homogeneous subsystems of the housing and communal services sector will obey the above-described patterns of functioning of the subsystems themselves. This means that when modeling dynamically nonequilibrium states of production activities of enterprises, the above-described patterns of taking into account the influence of multidirectional factors in the process of model formation can be used.

The relationship between the functional economic subsystems of the housing and communal services sector is realized through the exchange of prod-

ucts or services produced by them $u^i(t)$. Their volumes are determined depending on the current state

of each subsystem. In the general case, this relationship has a dynamic nature, since the available volumes of products or services appear as a result of the production process or the process of providing services, implemented over a certain period of time. However, for a better understanding of the essence of the proposed approach, we will initially assume that the relationship we are studying is static, that is,

$$u^i(t) = F^i(x^i(t)) \quad (4)$$

where F^i - production function of each subsystem, which is specified in advance.

Since the exchange of products or services is random, its result is random flows of products or services

$y_{ij}(t)$ between the functional economic subsystems of the housing and communal services sector i and j . Then the process of exchanging products or services itself can be characterized by a flow matrix [13]:

$$Y(t) = [y_{ij}(t)], i, j = 1, \dots, m \quad (5)$$

Thus, the state of the housing and communal services sector as a heterogeneous macrosystem will be determined by the state of the functional economic subsystems included in it $x(t) = \{x^1(t), \dots, x^m(t)\}$ and the state of the relationships between them, which are formed in the process of exchanging products or services, namely, the matrix of random flows $Y(t)$.

Since the housing and utilities sector is actually a dynamic heterogeneous macrosystem, it is necessary to take into account the time features of the processes under study $x(t)$ and $Y(t)$. In this case, the main idea of modeling nonequilibrium processes in heterogeneous macrosystems is the assumption that the change in the states of functional economic subsystems $x(t)$ occurs more slowly than the implementation of the processes of exchange of products or services $Y(t)$. Therefore, on a real-time scale, the dynamics of exchange processes can be replaced by a sequence of locally stationary states of functional economic subsystems.

$$H_F(N) = \sum_{n=1}^m N_n \ln \frac{N_n}{\tilde{\alpha}_n} + (G_n - N_n) \ln(G_n - N_n) \quad (7)$$

$$H_B(N) = \sum_{n=1}^m N_n \ln \frac{N_n}{e\alpha_n G_n} \quad (8)$$

Parameters of the processes of exchange of products or services α_{ij} , q_k , c_{ijk} may change over time depending on the organization of production processes in functional economic subsystems and at industry enterprises. This allows us to assume that the parameters of the distribution process depend on the state of the functional economic subsystems under consideration:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \alpha_{ij}(x(t)), q_k = q_k(x(t)), c_{ijk} = c_{ijk}(x(t)). \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha_{ij}(t)$ - a priori given probability;

$q_k(t)$ - volumes of exchanged products or services;

$c_{ijk}(t)$ - specific costs of exchanged products or services.

With regard to modeling the functional subsystems of the housing and communal services sector, the process of their change over time can be represented by a system of differential or difference equations, the right-hand side of which will depend on the current state of the economic subsystem $x(t)$ and the locally stationary distribution of flows of products or services $Y^*(t)$:

$$\frac{dx^i(t)}{dt} = F^i[x^i(t), Y^*(t)], i = 1, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

The functions F^i on the right side of these equations will be determined by the functional features of the corresponding economic subsystem of the housing and communal services sector.

Modeling using the proposed approach begins with fixing an arbitrary moment in time t . Since the exchange processes are random in nature, and the locally stationary states of this process are established over a small time interval Δt , then by the time $t + \Delta t$ a stationary distribution of the exchange process

will be established $Y^*(t)$. In this case, the mechanism of random distribution of the processes of exchange of products or services can be considered as a random and independent entry of some volumes of products or services into communication (i, j) with some a priori probability $\alpha_{ij}(t)$. Communication (i, j) in this case will be a set of close states with the corresponding volumes of exchange of products or services $G_{ij}\Delta t$, where G_{ij} is the maximum volume of exchange passing through communication (i, j) . Depending on the specific relationship of the functional economic subsystems under consideration, the volumes of exchange of products or services through communication (i, j) can reach the throughput G_{ij} (Fermi macrosystem) or be significantly lower than the throughput (Boltzmann macrosystem). In this case, the macro-state N of a random distribution of processes of exchange of products or services can be characterized by the generalized information entropies of Fermi or Boltzmann, respectively [13]:

The above considerations allow us to present a model of locally stationary distribution of nonequilibrium states of functional economic subsystems and industry enterprises in the following form:

$$H(Y, x(t)) \Rightarrow \max Y,$$

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^m c_{ijk}(x(t))y_{ij} = q_k(x(t)) \quad (10)$$

or

$$\sum_{i,j=1}^m c_{ijk}(x(t))y_{ij} \leq q_k(x(t)), k = 1, \dots, r$$

(11)
By combining expressions (6) and (11), we obtain a dynamic model of nonequilibrium states for

$$\frac{dx^i(t)}{dt} = F^i [x^i(t), Y^*(x(t))], i = 1, \dots, m;$$

$$Y^*(x(t)) = \arg \max \{H(Y, x(t)) | Y \in D(x(t))\} \quad (12)$$

where multitude $D(x(t))$ described either by a system of equalities or by a system of inequalities from (11).

Conclusion

Based on the obtained results, the following conclusions can be formulated:

1) the housing and utilities sector can be represented as a certain set of interconnected economic subsystems, each of which specializes in the implementation of a certain function;

2) the dynamics of interaction between enterprises within the functional subsystems in the process of comprehensive modernization of the housing and utilities sector can be described by a number of main arguments, which are time and spatial factors;

3) since the construction of dynamic models of nonequilibrium states of enterprise activity and the identification of their relationships with models of nonequilibrium states of activity of other economic entities is significantly complicated, it seems advisable to structure the housing and utilities sector into functional economic subsystems;

4) if the enterprises included in the functionally homogeneous subsystems of the housing and utilities sector obey the patterns disclosed in the article, they may well be used in modeling dynamic nonequilibrium states of production activities of these enterprises;

5) it was established that the relationship between the functional economic subsystems of the housing and utilities sector is realized through the exchange of products or services produced by them, the volumes of which are determined depending on the current state of each subsystem;

6) a dynamic model of nonequilibrium states for functional economic subsystems and sectoral enterprises of the housing and utilities sector was obtained, in which their distributions are described either by a system of equalities or by a system of inequalities.

Since the proposed approach takes into account to the maximum extent the real features of the process of exchanging products or services between functional economic subsystems and sectoral enterprises of the housing and utilities sector, it can be used in dynamic modeling of nonequilibrium states within the framework of development strategies of different subsystems and enterprises.

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